

The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob)

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The term "Chontal" is derived from the Nahuatl word *chontalli*, which means foreigners. This term has been applied to different ethnic groups in Mexico. The Chontal Maya are an indigenous group that inhabit the state of Tabasco, Mexico. They refer to themselves as *Yoko t'anob* and rose to prominence during the Postclassical period, although they can trace their roots back to the ancient Olmecs. They were renowned river and sea traders and lived in the floodplains and coastal zones of Tabasco. The Chontal Maya territory included rivers, lagoons, and marshes, which in turn shaped their economy, daily life, and spiritual worldview. Trade played a significant role in their society, as they transported goods such as cacao, salt, textiles, and ceramics by canoe, connecting inland and coastal Mesoamerican regions. They were considered an independent state within Mesoamerica, although they were subject to the Mexicas and were one of many cultures that had to pay a regular tribute. They believed in a universe made up of multiple layers, both vertical and horizontal. Their rituals, offerings, and ceremonies were directed toward maintaining balance between humans, nature, and the supernatural. Spirits, deities, and natural forces had to be respected and appeased through proper conduct and observance of traditional customs. Some of these practices included human sacrifice, blood-letting rituals and ritualistic piercing of body parts. Many Chontal Mayan communities continue to maintain their language, customs, and practices and have resisted pressures of assimilation. These communities are still considered authentic and distinct Maya people in modern-day Mexico.

Date Range: 250 CE - 1521 CE

Region: Tabasco Wetlands

Region tags: Maya, Mexico

The Chontal Maya have historically been located in the lower Grijalva River basin and the wetlands of Tabasco, Mexico

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Fuente 1: S. Thompson, J. E. *The Rise and Fall of Maya Civilization*. England: University of Oklahoma Press, 1956.
- Fuente 2: Hernández Granada, A. *Los Chontales Prehispánicos de Tabasco-Campeche: En Busca de Su Identidad Étnica*. Tesis de Maestría en Estudios Mesoamericanos. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2018.
- Fuente 3: Izquierdo, A. L. *Acalán y La Chontalpa En El Siglo XVI. Su Geografía Política*. México: Centro de Estudios Mayas, Instituto de Investigaciones Filológicas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 1997

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- URL de la Fuente 1: https://www.gob.mx/cms/uploads/attachment/file/11021/chontales_tabasco.pdf
- Descripción de la Fuente 1: Flores López, J.M. *Chontales de Tabasco*. Mexico: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2006
- URL de la Fuente 2: https://www.academia.edu/996245/VASQUEZ_DAVILA_and_HIPOLITO_1994_La_cosmovisi%C3%B3n_de_los_chontales_de_Tabasco
- Descripción de la Fuente 2: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión de Los Chontales de Tabasco: Notas Preliminares." *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).
- URL de la Fuente 3: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321595523_New_Perspectives_on_Human_Sacrifice_and_Ritual_Body_Treatments_in_Ancient_Maya_Society
- Descripción de la Fuente 3: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. New York: Springer, 2006

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

–URL de la Fuente 1: <https://archive.org/details/mayachontalindia00scho/page/272/mode/2up>

–Descripción de la Fuente 1: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-Tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula. Oklahoma Press , 1968

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Sí

Notes: The origin of the Chontales of Acalán (Mayan Chontal) can be traced to a Nahua-speaking group whom, after being displaced, had to fight for territory in which to settle. They became a militarized society and eventually seized control of the region's capital, which they named Itzamkanac. The Chontal Mayan within Acalan region can also trace their origins to upper Yucatan mayan groups. Scholes and Roys (1968) also document that the Chontal Mayan would pay tribute to the Mexica up until the Spanish arrival.

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula. Oklahoma Press , 1968.

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Sí

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Sí

Notes: Researchers have noted that during their period of expansion the Chontal Mayan co-existed with several groups. They engaged in battle with some of them in order to gain control over the settlements . These engagements were, at least partly, inspired by a need to compete over strategic resources, like the Usumacinta river routes (Muñoz-Salinas, 2018).

Reference: Muñoz-Salinas, E., D. Cook, M. Castillo, T. Beach, and S. Luzzadder-Beach. "Four Millennia of Geomorphic Change and Human Settlement in the Lower Usumacinta-grijalva River Basin, Mexico." *Progress in Physical Geography: Earth and Environment* 47, no. 2 (2023).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: The Chontal did not have a formal process for religious affiliation. Instead, affiliation was implicit, tied to one's birthright within the community. Each town operated as part of a confederation of settlements, where local rulers held both civic and religious authority, making formal affiliation unnecessary (Scholes & Roy, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula. Oklahoma Press , 1968.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The evidence suggests that the integration of religion and their practices did not rely on outreach or proselytize efforts, rather it was facilitated through the military overrun of subdued towns or settlements (Faudree, 2015).

Reference: Faudree, P. "Made in Translation: Revisiting the Chontal Maya Account of the Conquest. *Ethnohistory*", 2015.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Authority was exercised not by separate religious and civil leaders, but by local chiefs called *batabo'ob*, who held both spiritual and administrative responsibilities (Scholes & Roy, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence of individuals rejecting belief; however, since religious practice was tied to communal identity, abandoning it would have meant breaking with the community and facing the social consequences (Jiménez Abollado, 2022).

Reference: Jiménez Abollado, F. "Bernal Díaz Del Castillo Y "sus" Conquistas De Tabasco, 1517-1525". *EDÄHI Boletín Científico De Ciencias Sociales Y Humanidades Del Icshu*, no. 10 (2022).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 4500

Notes: There is consensus amongst researchers that Ytzamkanac (the capital of Tamactún-Acalán) hosted around 4500 people at all times. Some researchers have also argued that Acalán carried a territorial influence that included a list of 76 subordinate towns (Ciudad Ruiz and Lacadena García-Gallo, 2001; Scholes and Roys, 1948), meaning the overall Chontal Maya population could have been vastly superior in size.

Reference: Ciudad Ruiz, A., and A. Lacadena García-Gallo. "Tamactún-acalán: Interpretación De Una Hegemonía Política Maya De Los Siglos XIV-XVI", no. 87 (2001).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Chontal Maya's religious traditions were deeply embedded with community and social relations. Being a Chontal Maya meant being part of a cultural, social and religious way of life. Like most of the civilizations from Mesoamerica, it is highly unlikely that members of the community practiced other religions.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: While the Maya civilization developed one of the most complex hieroglyphic writing systems in the ancient world, there is no evidence of codices or fully developed glyphic texts native to the Chontal region of Tabasco. However, several monuments at sites like Pomoná bear Maya-style glyphs that may suggest external influence and interaction with central lowland Maya traditions (Culbert, 1991).

Reference: Culbert, P. *Classic Maya Political History: Hieroglyphs and Archaeological Evidence*. Cambridge University Press, 1991.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

— Sí

Notes: Itzamkanac is perceived by many as the capital of the Chontal Mayan and home to the main temple (Scholes and Roys, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula. Oklahoma Press , 1968.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

— Sí

Notes: The site of Itzamkanac stood out as a significant ceremonial center, described by Hernán Cortés as a flourishing city with numerous temples (Scholes and Roys, 1968). In front of these, altars (often low, rectangular stone platforms) were used for offerings and sacrificial ceremonies.

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula. Oklahoma Press , 1968.

↳ Tombs:
— Field doesn't know

↳ Cemeteries:
— No

↳ Temples:
— Yes

↳ Altars:
— Yes

↳ Devotional markers:
— Field doesn't know

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
— Sí
Notes: Temples, such as the one in Itzamkanac, functioned as mass gathering spaces where community rituals, dances, and public ceremonies were held (Scholes and Roys, 1968).
Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula. Oklahoma Press , 1968.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
— No

Is iconography present:

— Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:
— En el hogar
— Únicamente en espacios religiosos públicos
— En algunos espacios públicos

Notes: There is evidence of iconographic elements within "Figurines". These were made as

representations of deities, and possessed ritual gestures and symbolic attributes related to fertility, death, and transformation, among others (Gallegos Gómora and Armijo Torres, 2022).

Reference: Gallegos Gómora, M.J., and R. Armijo Torres. "Las Figurillas Mayas De Tabasco, México: Contextos Y Narraciones Del Clásico Tardío". *Figurines*, no. 6 (2021).

- ↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:
– Yes

- ↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...
 - Yes

Notes: Itzamkanac, originally known as "Place of the Iguana/Crocodile House" in Chontal Maya was known as the capital of the civilization (Scholes et al., 1968) It's located on a hill overlooking the Candelaria River in southern Campeche, which connects Guatemala's Petén region and Calakmul to the Gulf of Mexico, served as a vital trade and communication route (Maestri, 2018).

Are pilgrimages present:
– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Sí

Notes: The human being is composed of three elements: the soul (ánima), the shadow (bo'di), and the body (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994). The soul is associated with the heart (pishan) and only leaves the body at the moment of death. The shadow can temporarily leave the body while the person is still alive. Both the soul and the shadow leave the body permanently after one's death.

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Sí (especifique): The shadow (bo'di)

Notes: The shadow can leave the body while a person is still alive, this was generally considered involuntary and typically occurred when a Chontal individual fell ill due to fright (susto). It is also believed that a "duende" (a supernatural being) can seize a person's shadow, making them vulnerable to illness (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994).

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

Belief in afterlife:

— Sí

Notes: Rather than remaining in the world of the living, the souls of the deceased are believed to inhabit a distinct, otherworldly realm (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994). Chontal Maya also believed that the soul could sometimes roam as an unsettled spirit after departing the body.

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

— Sí

Notes: The yoko yinikob (or Chontal Maya) conceive the universe as three separate levels or planes arranged along a vertical axis. The Chontal territory lies in the middle (land, rivers and sea). Below is the subterranean world or underworld, and above is the sky. There is also a horizontal dimension, defined by the four cardinal directions: east, west, north, and south. (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994).

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

— Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

— Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

— Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

— Yes

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

— No

Reincarnation in this world:

— No

Notes: According to their worldview, once both the soul and the shadow had left the body permanently, there was no return (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994). There is evidence of Chontal performing rituals, such as nine days of prayer, to retrieve the shadow. These were practiced not to bring the person back, but to help the spirit cease wandering and move on to the next existential plane. There are also ethnohistorical studies that claim the shadows would return once a year in order to visit the living.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

— Yes

↳ Interment:

— Yes

Notes: Van Broekhoven (1995) describes the customs and beliefs about death in Tamulté (a Chontal town). In this account, she explains that the dead are first bathed and dressed in their finest clothes before being buried. The deceased are wrapped in a petate (woven mat) along with their belongings, wearing huaraches for the journey they must walk, and carrying some

food to feed the spirits they will encounter.

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Researchers found that co-sacrifice is present in Mesoamerican funerary traditions, however there is no evidence or myth explaining this within the Chontal Maya traditions specifically (Van Broekhoven, 1995).

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

Are grave goods present:

– Sí

Notes: In current Chontal burial practices, deceased men, before their death, would choose which personal object to take with them, such as a machete or a sombrero (Van Broekhoven, 1995). Both men and women must carry a jícara, pozol, and small tortillas; it is believed that with these offerings, the dead will be able to reach their destination.

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

↳ Personal effects:
– Yes

↳ Valuable items:
– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):
– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:
– No

↳ Other grave goods:
– No

Are formal burials present:

– Sí

Notes: Although there are records of burials found within certain temples, researchers have determined that these burials belonged to elites and noble families (Geller et al., 2006). It is believed that the deceased from families outside this social class were buried in spaces within their household patios.

Reference: Geller, P., K. Reese-Taylor, and M. Zender. Fit to Be Tied: Funerary Practices Among the Prehispanic Maya, 2006.

↳ As cenotaphs:
– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Sí

Notes: There is evidence that Chontal cosmology was shaped by a diverse set of beliefs in the supernatural world. These beliefs may be intertwined with ideologies from nearby regions, such as the Yucatecan Maya (Yucatán, Campeche and Quintana Roo). Researchers have found that the Chontales believed their lives were guided by these beings. They worshipped gods like Aj Chawäk (God of Thunder) and Ek Chuah (God of Cacao), who were seen as providers for their agricultural needs (Lorente Fernández, 2016). Other entities, such as "duendes", were believed to maintain the natural order of forests and rivers (Fergus and Hull, 2013). Oral traditions passed down through generations also reflect the Chontal belief in spirits (Rubio and Martínez, 2006).

Reference: Lorente Fernández, D.. *Mythology and Multifunctionality of Thunder God Among the Chontal of Tabasco*. México: Dirección de Etnología y Antropología Social, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Ciudad de México, 2016.

Reference: Fergus, R., and K. Hull. "Ethno-ornithological Research Among the Chontal Maya of Tabasco, Mexico", 2013.

Reference: Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espiritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Sí

Notes: There is no singular supreme deity. Religious practice centered on a plurality of gods, each associated with specific ecological domains. These deities are characterized by distinct attributes and had specialized areas of influence (Lorente Fernández, 2016; Hernández Granada, 2018).

Reference: Lorente Fernández, D.. *Mythology and Multifunctionality of Thunder God Among the Chontal of Tabasco*. México: Dirección de Etnología y Antropología Social, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Ciudad de México, 2016.

Reference: Hernández Granada, A.. *Los Chontales Prehispánicos De Tabasco-campeche : En Busca De Su Identidad Étnica*. Tesis de Maestría en Estudios Mesoamericanos. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México , 2018.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: According to orally transmitted myths within one Chontal settlement, it is believed that human spirits returned towards the end of the year. During this time, families prepared a table with offerings for the deceased, including their favorite meals and personal objects. However, no one truly knows who returns from the other side, as they are said to come back in the form of large shadows (Rubio and Martínez, 2006).

Reference: Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espíritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Ethnohistorical works have collected stories about sudden noises or unexplained movements that would occur with no apparent cause, though it is uncertain if these narratives can be traced back to the pre-Columbian Chontal Mayan.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Sí

Notes: Human spirits would sometimes return for specific offerings, such as their favorite foods or objects, and recognize the homes or spaces they once inhabited (Rubio and Martínez, 2006).

Reference: Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espíritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Sí

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Sí

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Sí

Notes: Spirit can cause harm (frighten, disturb sleep, or bring illness) when they are neglected or disrespected, particularly if not properly honored during ritual dates. Narratives suggest that when properly honored, spirits do not cause harm and may allow peace or well-being to return to the household (Rubio and Martínez, 2006).

Reference: Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espíritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006.

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ In dreams:

– Sí

Notes: Dreams serve as a primary channel through which spirits deliver messages to their family members, often to express their needs, such as the desire to be remembered or be offered food. They could also issue warnings of potential danger (Rubio and Martínez, 2006).

Reference: Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espíritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006.

↳ In trance possession:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Through divination processes:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Only through specialists:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Only through monarch:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Sí

Notes: Researchers have documented the presence of non-human supernatural beings in Chontal cosmology. Birds can sometimes be regarded as omens or messengers, foretellers of illness or rain (Kerry & Fergus, 2013); Incháustegui (1987) recorded that maize was believed to possess a soul. Vásquez Dávila and Hernández (1994) described the existence of "duendes" or Ch'ujob (also translated as "idols") who can "seize a person's shadow", making them vulnerable to illness. Kooyak, known as "the one who causes laughter," is another entity said to kill and eat people. Both Kooyak's and Ch'ujob's original role was to protect the tropical ecosystem and its balance.

Reference: Fergus, R., and K. Hull. "Ethno-ornithological Research Among the Chontal Maya of Tabasco, Mexico", 2013.

Reference: Incháustegui, C.. Las Márgenes Del Tabasco Chontal. Mexico: Gobierno del Estado de Tabasco, 1987.

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". América Indígena 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Sí

Notes: Both types of duendes have specific areas of influence. The ch'ujob are said to "take a person's shadow", a spiritual act that causes illness, weakness, or soul loss, it occurred when someone disrespects ritual boundaries or enters sacred spaces improperly. Kooyak, described as "the one who causes laughter," kills and devours people who disrupt the balance of the forest (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994).

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Sí
 - Notes: Kooyak are active agents with perceptive awareness of human transgressions (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994).
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Duendes possess environmental, spiritual, and moral knowledge of the world.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - No
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Duendes are not described as emotionally driven.
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Notes: Kooyak are described as beings that kill and consume humans, suggesting a form of hunger that carries symbolic or supernatural significance.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there is no evidence that Chontal leaders were considered deities, their political and religious roles were closely intertwined (Scholes & Roys, 1968). They acted as sacred intermediaries with ritual authority, contributing to the maintenance of cosmic and social order

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Sí

Notes: According to Vásquez Dávila and Hernández (1994), the Chontal Maya of Tabasco cosmology includes a wide variety of beings such as deities, spirits, and nature guardians. Ix Bolom, the moon goddess, is associated with fertility and healing (Sigal, 2000), while the Bolom Tikú, governs the underworld.

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

Reference: Sigal, P.. *From Moon Goddesses to Virgins. The Colonization of Yucatecan Maya Sexual Desire*. Texas: University of Texas Press , 2000.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Sí

Notes: Ix Bolom is known to be the sun's wife and twin (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994), and grandmother to zutz balum, which are bat-jaguar men (Campos, 1988).

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

Reference: Campos, J.. *Bajo El Signo De Ix Bolon*. México: Fondo de Cultura Económica-Instituto de Cultura de Tabasco, 1988.

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Sí

Notes: The Chontal think of the cosmos as a layered structure with three vertical realms: the heavens above, the earthly domain in the middle, and the underworld below. This spatial organization is framed horizontally by the directions of the natural world: east, west, north, and south. In each level, they recognize different entities believed to possess a diversity of powers and influence (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994).

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Sí

Notes: Each being is responsible for a distinct domain within nature or the cosmos. For instance, Ix Bolom is associated with the moon, water, and fertility; the yumka' oversee forests and agricultural growth; Aj Zutz Balum is connected to night and abundance; and the Bolom Tikú rule over matters of death and disease in the underworld (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994).

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Researchers agree that the Chontal of Tabasco shared deities with other Mesoamerican traditions. In the archaeological site of Comalcalco, Tabasco, stucco reliefs depict nine figures interpreted as the Bolom Tikú, or Nine Lords of the Night, who are also associated with the underworld and the broader Mayan Pantheon of deities (Mejía Perez Campos, 1992).

Reference: Mejía Perez Campos, E. "Comalcalco". *Arqueología*. Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia - INAH, 1992.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Sí

Notes: Creatures such as "duendes" possessed the capacity to monitor and influence human behavior (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández, 1994), and some deities like Aj Chawäk, associated with rain and thunder and creator of water bodies, were intertwined with agriculture and, in some cases, human sickness (Lorente Fernández, 2016).

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

Reference: Lorente Fernández, D.. *Mythology and Multifunctionality of Thunder God Among the Chontal of Tabasco*. México: Dirección de Etnología y Antropología Social, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Ciudad de México, 2016.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Sí

Notes: Lorente Fernández (2016) describes myths in which Aj Chawäk would manifest in moments where society was not behaving according to group norms.

Reference: Lorente Fernández, D.. *Mythology and Multifunctionality of Thunder God Among the Chontal of Tabasco*. México: Dirección de Etnología y Antropología Social, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Ciudad de México, 2016.

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Sí

Notes: Van Broekhoven (1995) describes stories centered in Tamulté (Chontal town), where people entered forests or took natural items without ritual acknowledgment or permission. They were later punished by supernatural beings.

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. *La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad*. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Sí

Notes: Researchers found that Chontales believed improper or absent ritual practice was seen by supernatural beings as a breakdown in their relationship. Supernatural beings actively tried to remedy the situation through different actions (Van Broekhoven, 1995).

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. *La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad*. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Sí

Notes: Researches have argued that deities needed to be venerated through ritual acts and ceremonies to access natural resources (Fita et al., 2015), while spirits must be acknowledged to cross to the other side and not disturb living humans (Rubio and Martínez, 2006).

Reference: Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espíritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006.

Reference: Fita, D., E. Naranjo, E. Estrada-Lugo, R. Mariaca, and E. Bello. "Symbolism and Ritual Practices Related to Hunting in Maya Communities from Central Quintana Roo, Mexico." *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 11 (2015).

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Sí

Notes: Some misfortunes, like floods or hurricanes, were interpreted as punishments directed at the community (Van Broekhoven, 1995).

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Sí

Notes: Some Chontal myths have detailed how individuals (including children) may be punished for misbehaving or acting with arrogance (Van Broekhoven, 1995).

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Done randomly:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Other [specify]
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings are believed to bestow rewards such as health, protection, and access to

natural abundance when treated properly (Van Broekhoven, 1995).

Reference: Van Broekhoven, L. La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No
 - ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: Chontal system is focused on reciprocity, and balance, rather than on salvation by a divine entity (Vásquez Dávila and Hernández , 1994).

Reference: Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Although beliefs regarding the soul (pixan), the underworld, and spiritual entities are present, they are primarily associated with ritual duties and sustaining cosmic balance, rather than forming part of a clearly defined eschatological framework (Van Broekhoven, 1995).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Sí

Notes: Researchers think that rulers held a position in which political and religious roles were deeply intertwined (Lacadena and Ciudad Ruiz, 1998). Ringle and Stuart's (1998) translations of the adjective k'u(l) meaning "sacred" and interpretation of ahaw as "the highest governmental authority", are some examples of works that have contributed to this common belief within academia.

Reference: Lacadena, A., and A. Ciudad Ruiz. "Reflexiones Sobre Estructura Política Maya Clásica". In *Anatomía De Una Civilización. Aproximaciones Interdisciplinarias a La Cultura Maya*. España: Sociedad Española de Estudios Mayas, 1998.

Reference: Ringle, W. M., and C.E. Stuart. *Of Mice and Monkeys: The Value and Meaning of T1016, the God C Hieroglyph*. United States of America: Center for Maya Research, 1988.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Some researchers argue that certain rituals required sexual purification before being performed - abstaining from sexual relations (Gonlin and Lohse, 2007; Tiesler and Cucina, 2006). Pete Sigal (2000), however, has argued that sexuality was an active part of ritual discourse and performance, with all sex acts carrying a specific symbolic weight.

Reference: Gonlin, N., and J.C. Lohse. *Commoner Ritual and Ideology in Ancient Mesoamerica*. Colorado: University Press of Colorado, 2007.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Reference: Sigal, P.. *From Moon Goddesses to Virgins. The Colonization of Yucatecan Maya Sexual Desire*. Texas: University of Texas Press , 2000.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence in academic literature that Chontal Mayan religious roles required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Sí

Notes: Broader Mayan religious traditions involved fasting before certain ceremonies (Tiesler and Cucina, 2006; Tozzer, 1941). It is likely that this practice was also present in Chontal Mayan religious traditions.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Reference: Tozzer, A.M.. *Landa's Relación De Los Cosas De Yucatán*. Cambridge: Harvard University, 1941.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Sí

Notes: Rules and general concerns were closely followed by all participants before, during, and after the performance of human sacrifice to ensure the effectiveness of the rite. Some of these included fasting and autosacrifice (López, 1988; Nájera, 1987; Tiesler and Cucina, 2006).

Reference: López, A.. "Los Ritos. Un Juego De Definiciones". *Arqueología Mexicana*, no. 34 (1988): 4-17.

Reference: Nájera, M.I.. *El Don De La Sangre En El Equilibrio Cósmico*. Mexico City: Centro de Estudios Mayas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 1987.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Cranial deformation and modified teeth have been found in burial sites (Tiesler and Cucina, 2006) and are well documented by researchers. However, they are not explicitly tied to religious initiation or requirements for belonging to a priesthood or the religious group. Landa (1982), a 16th century Spanish priest, noted that some individuals sometimes pierced their cheeks, their ears, genitals, or their lower lips and drew straw through holes made in their tongues.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Reference: Landa, Fray D.. *Relación De Las Cosas De Yucatán, [sixteenth Century]*. Mexico City: Porrúa, 1982.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

— Sí

Notes: Bloodletting via piercing (tongue, ear, genitals) was common among priesthood for ritual communication with deities (Joralemon, 1974).

Reference: Joralemon, D.. "Ritual Blood-sacrifice Among the Ancient Maya, Part I". *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 118, no. 2 (1974): 59-106.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— Sí

Notes: Human sacrifice was common in the Chontal Maya region. Ritual killing involved tearing out the heart of prisoners and wrongdoers. (Joralemon, 1974; Tiesler and Cucina, 2006). Endowment then followed it, as the heart and blood were collected and handed to the high priest who offered them to the gods while invoking the supernatural. Children and young adults were sometimes sacrificed as innocents in other Maya regions, particularly in cave contexts of the southern lowlands (Scott and Brady, 2005). It is unknown whether these practices extended to the Mayan of the Chontal region.

Reference: Joralemon, D.. "Ritual Blood-sacrifice Among the Ancient Maya, Part I". *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 118, no. 2 (1974): 59-106.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Reference: Scott, A.M., and J.E. Brady. "Human Remains in Lowland Maya Caves: Problems of Interpretation". In *Stone Houses and Earth Lords: Maya Religion in the Cave Context*. Boulder: University Press of Colorado, 2005.

↳ Foreign, slaves:

— Sí

↳ Commoners:

— Sí

↳ Elites:

— No

↳ Other:

— No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— Sí

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence that points towards self-sacrifice or suicide practices within the Chontal Mayan.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: In broader Maya society, priests and elites placed valuable offerings, some examples are jade, ceremonial pottery, obsidian blades, and symbolic bundles (Geller et al., 2006). Decorated corpses have also been found with incusted jade around their teeth and bodies (Tiesler and Cucina, 2006). It is likely that the Chontal Mayan followed these ritual practices, although there are no concrete studies on pre-Columbian Chontal Mayan practices that confirm these.

Reference: Geller, P., K. Reese-Taylor, and M. Zender. *Fit to Be Tied: Funerary Practices Among the Prehispanic Maya*, 2006.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Sí

Notes: Ritual schedules were tied to the 260 day calendar. The population was expected to attend ritual events and take part in ritualistic practices (Tiesler and Cucina, 2006; Landa, 1982; Scholes and Roys, 1968), which in turn entailed a significant time commitment.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Reference: Landa, Fray D.. *Relación De Las Cosas De Yucatán, [sixteenth Century]*. Mexico City: Porrúa, 1982.

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Sí

Notes: Self-inflicted bloodletting via piercing tongues, ears, or genitals has been documented by several researchers (Munson et al., 2014; McLeod, 2019). Ritual acts of blood sacrifice are believed to be a central duty for divine Maya kings. Some researchers believe these were necessary rites of passage that legitimated an individual's right to rule (Stuart, 1984).

Reference: Munson, J., V. Amati, M. Collard, and M.J. Macri. "Classic Maya Bloodletting and the Cultural Evolution of Religious Rituals: Quantifying Patterns of Variation in Hieroglyphic Texts". *Plos One* 9, no. 9 (2014).

Reference: McLeod, A.. "Sacrifice: A Maya Conception of a Misunderstood and Underappreciated Component of Well-being". *Science, Religion and Culture* 6, no. 1 (2019): 34-41.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Sí

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Sí

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– El campo lo desconoce

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:
i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Sí

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: Studies estimate that large scale rituals correlated with settlement populations. In broader Mayan civilization, “Plazas” (public areas where large-scale rituals would take place), could often accommodate hundreds to thousands of people (Lucero, 2003).

Reference: Lucero, L.J.. “The Politics of Ritual. The Emergence of Classic Maya Rulers”. *Current Anthropology* 44, no. 4 (2003): 523-58.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: The Mayan calendar organized ceremonies by days, not hours. There is no documented hourly breakdown of ritual sequences.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Sí

Notes: Ritual precision was critical. Offerings needed to be placed in the right spaces and the rituals had to be done with clear steps. In human sacrifice rituals, for instance, Landa (1982) described that the priests would tear out the heart in specific ways, and would have to immediately point it at the sky as an offering.

Reference: Landa, Fray D.. *Relación De Las Cosas De Yucatán*, [sixteenth Century]. Mexico City: Porrúa, 1982.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Sí

Notes: Group performances (chants, processions, communal dances) were an integral component of the rituals in plaza events (Inomata, 2006).

Reference: Inomata, T.. “Plazas, Performers, and Spectators: Political Theaters of the Classic Maya”. *Current Anthropology* 47, no. 5 (2006): 805-42.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Sí

Notes: Archaeobotanical and iconographic evidence confirms the use of psychoactive plants (morning-glory seeds, chili peppers, and xtabentún) in ritual contexts, possibly to induce trance or connecting to the supernatural (Lentz et al., 2024; Blainey, 2016).

Reference: Lentz, D.L., T.L. Hamilton, S.A. Meyers, N.P. Dunning, K. Reese-Taylor, A.A. Hernández, D.S. Walker, E.J. Tepe, A.F. Esquivel, and A.A. Weiss. “Psychoactive and Other Ceremonial Plants from a 2,000-year-old Maya Ritual Deposit at Yaxnohcah, Mexico”. *Plos One* 19, no. 4 (2024).

Reference: Blainey, M.G.. “Techniques of Luminosity: Iron-ore Mirrors and Entheogenic

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Sí

↳ Tattoos/scarification:
– Sí

↳ Circumcision:
– No

↳ Food taboos:
– Sí

↳ Hair:
– No

↳ Dress:
– Sí

↳ Ornaments:
– Sí

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– No

↳ Other:
– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– El campo lo desconoce

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Un estado

Notes: The presence of a centralized capital at Itzamkanac, a hierarchical political structure, and a tributary system (Scholes and Roys, 1968) suggests they operated as an independent state.

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence suggesting there was an organized famine relief system.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: No institutional aid to the poor is described by pre-colonial sources. Scholes and Roys (1968) and Landa (1982) describe cases in which wealth and tribute flowed toward elites and the priesthood, rather than commoners.

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Reference: Landa, Fray D.. *Relación De Las Cosas De Yucatán, [sixteenth Century]*. Mexico City: Porrúa, 1982.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no recorded system of institutional elder or sick care.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– El campo lo desconoce

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– El campo lo desconoce

Notes: There is no evidence of organized, pre-conquest formal education provided by Chontal religious authorities.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– El campo lo desconoce

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Sí

Notes: The Chontal Maya of Acalan-Tixchel had a structured administrative-religious hierarchy, including officials such as batabob (local leaders), halach uinic (main lord), and priests. These roles involved managing tribute, ceremonies, and daily governance (Scholes and Roys, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Sí

Notes: The Chontal had diplomatic, economic, and religious dealings with the Mexica (Aztec) and neighboring Maya states (Scholes and Roys, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

— Sí

Notes: Food storage (granaries) was managed by elites like the halach uinic and batabob for tributary or ritual redistribution (Scholes and Roys, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— Sí

Notes: The halach uinic, batabob, and assemblies coordinated waterworks, irrigation, and canoe routes (Scholes and Roys, 1968; Lucero, 2002).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Reference: Lucero, L.J.. "The Collapse of the Classic Maya: A Case for the Role of Water Control". *American Anthropologist* 104, no. 3 (2002): 814-26.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— Sí

Notes: Water transport infrastructure was prevalent in the Chontal Mayan area of Acatlan. These routes were comprised by canals and navigable routes and were maintained and overseen by the halach uinic and batabob (Scholes and Roys, 1968). Trade routes between the Chontal Mayan and other Mesoamerican civilizations have also been documented by researchers (Lucero, 2002).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Reference: Lucero, L.J.. "The Collapse of the Classic Maya: A Case for the Role of Water Control". *American Anthropologist* 104, no. 3 (2002): 814-26.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

— Sí

Notes: The halach uinic and subordinate officials collected tribute for redistribution and ritual use. These often included cacao, cloth, and foodstuffs, for redistribution and ritual use (Scholes and Roys, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Sí

Notes: Tribute was also sent to external powers, notably the Mexica (Scholes and Roys, 1968).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Sí

Notes: The batabob (local chiefs) managed public order. Tupiles (local guards) enforced local decrees and maintaining peace (Scholes and Roys, 1968)

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Sí

Notes: The halach uinic, advised by local chiefs (batabob), administered justice (Landa, 1982).

Reference: Landa, Fray D.. *Relación De Las Cosas De Yucatán, [sixteenth Century]*. Mexico City: Porrúa, 1982.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Sí

Notes: Infractions such as theft, murder, or tribute evasion were punished through physical means (execution, enslavement), material penalties (confiscation of goods), or public shaming (haircutting). Some wrongdoers would also be punished by becoming human sacrifices for deities (Scholes and Roys, 1968; Roys, 1957; Tiesler and Cucina, 2006).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Reference: Roys, R.L.. *The Political Geography of the Yucatan Maya*. Washington: Carnegie Institution of Washington, 1957.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Sí

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Sí

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Sí

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: Roys (1957) describes Maya customary law as "structured, hereditary, and formal", despite its oral and non-codified form. Customary law was administered by the halach uinic and batabob. There is no surviving codified legal document but it is known that they operated according to established rules, hereditary office, and known procedures.

Reference: Roys, R.L.. *The Political Geography of the Yucatan Maya*. Washington: Carnegie Institution of Washington, 1957.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Sí

Notes: The halach uinic (supreme ruler) held the political and military authority and appointed local governors (batabob) to administer towns and raise militias. There are also mentions of the Nacom as a specialized military leader, in charge of commanding armed forces (Scholes and Roys, 1968). Other researchers have also related the role of Nacom to that of an "executioner" (Tiesler and Cucina, 2006).

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel: a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Reference: Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– El campo lo desconoce

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Sí

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Sí

Notes: The Maya hieroglyphic system was the main writing method across all Classic Maya regions, including the Chontal Mayan. It was mainly used by scribes and elite classes, including priests. It would be used to describe royal lineage, political events, economic transactions and religious descriptions. This language was widely used across Mayan regions (Kettunen and Helmke, 2019)

Reference: Kettunen, h., and C. Helmke. Introduction to Maya Hieroglyphs: 10th European Maya Workshop Handbook. Leiden: Wayeb and Leiden University, 2010.

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Sí

Notes: The Chontal Maya followed the 260 day calendar that was prevalent to Mesoamerica and other Mayan groups. Though still debated, the origins of the calendar system can be traced back to the Olmec civilization, somewhere between 800 BCE and 400 BCE (Šprajc et al., 2023)

Reference: Šprajc, I., T. Inomata, and A.F. Aveni. "Origins of Mesoamerican Astronomy and Calendar: Evidence from the Olmec and Maya Regions". *Science Advances* 9, no. 1 (2023).

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Sí

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pesca

– Agricultura a pequeña escala/jardines hortícolas o huertos

– Agricultura a gran escala (ej. monocultivos, sistemas de irrigación organizados)

Notes: The Chontal Maya produced and managed their own food resources. As detailed by Scholes & Roys (1968), they cultivated maize, beans, native fruits, and managed staple food production independently. They were also widely known as expert fishermen.

Reference: Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Scholes, F., and R. Roys. The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalantixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula. Oklahoma Press , 1968.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Torras Conangla, R.M.. Espacios De Resistencia Y Colonización. La Construcción Territorial Del México Republicano Desde La Localidad De Palizada, En El Suroeste De La Península De Yucatán (1821-1916). México: Tesis Doctoral en Estudios Mesoamericanos. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Instituto de Investigaciones Filológicas, 2010.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Vargas, E.. Itzamkanac Y Acalan. Tiempos De Crisis Anticipando El Futuro.. México: Instituto de Investigaciones Antropológicas. Universidad Nacional de México., 2001.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), S. Thompson, J. E.. The Rise and Fall of Maya Civilization. England: University of Oklahoma Press, 1956.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Balcells González, J.A.. Patrones De Asentamiento Y Territorios Prehispánicos En La Región De Salto De Agua : Formas De Habitar Y Organizar El Espacio Al Poniente Del Señorío De B'aakal. Tesis Doctoral. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 2011.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Gallegos Gómora, M.J., and R. Armijo Torres. "Las Figurillas Mayas De Tabasco, México: Contextos Y Narraciones Del Clásico Tardío". *Figurines*, no. 6 (2021).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Muñoz-Salinas, E., D. Cook, M. Castillo, T. Beach, and S. Luzzadder-Beach. "Four Millennia of Geomorphic Change and Human Settlement in the Lower Usumacinta-grijalva River Basin, Mexico.". *Progress in Physical Geography: Earth and Environment* 47, no. 2 (2023).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Maestri, N.. From Movement to Mobility: The Archaeology of Boca Chinikihá (mexico), a Riverine Settlement in the Usumacinta Region. Doctoral Dissertation of Philosophy in Anthropology. University of California Riverside, 2018.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Ciprian, A.. "Before the End of the World: Archaeological Investigations About Maya Terminal Classic Processes on the Middle Candelaria River, Campeche, Mexico.". *Studii De Preistorie* 5 (2008): 171-205.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Weeks, J.M.. "The Carnegie Maya IV : Carnegie Institution of Washington Theoretical Approaches to Problems". University Press of Colorado, 2012.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Peck, D. T. . "The Geographical Origin and Acculturation of Maya Advanced Civilization in Mesoamerica.". *Revista De Historia De América*, no. 130 (2002).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Geller, P., K. Reese-Taylor, and M. Zender. *Fit to Be Tied: Funerary Practices Among the Prehispanic Maya*, 2006.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Ciudad Ruiz, A., and A. Lacadena García-Gallo. "Tamactún-acalán: Interpretación De Una Hegemonía Política Maya De Los Siglos XIV-XVI", no. 87 (2001).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Ringle, W. M., and G.E. Stuart. *Of Mice and Monkeys: The Value and Meaning of T1016, the God C Hieroglyph*.. United States of America: Center for Maya Research, 1988.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Demarest, A. A.. "Ideology in Ancient Maya Cultural Evolution: The Dynamics of Galactic Polities". In *Ideology and Pre-columbian Civilization*. School of American Research Press, 1992.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Grube, N., and M. Simon. "Política Clásica Maya Dentro De Una Tradición Mesoamericana: Un Modelo Epigráfico De Organización Política "hegemónica"". In *Modelos De Entidades Políticas Mayas*, edited by S. Trejo. México: INAH, 1998.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Izquierdo, A. L.. *Acalán Y La Chontalpa En El Siglo XVI. Su Geografía Política*. México: Centro de Estudios Mayas, Instituto de Investigaciones Filológicas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 1997.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Lacadena, A., and A. Ciudad Ruiz. "Reflexiones Sobre Estructura Política Maya Clásica". In *Anatomía De Una Civilización. Aproximaciones Interdisciplinarias a La Cultura Maya*. España: Sociedad Española de Estudios Mayas, 1998.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Culbert , P.. *Classic Maya Political History: Hieroglyphs and Archaeological Evidence*. Cambridge University Press, 1991.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Faudree, P.. "Made in Translation: Revisiting the Chontal Maya

Account of the Conquest. *Ethnohistory*, 2015.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Jiménez Abollado, F.. "Bernal Díaz Del Castillo Y "sus" Conquistas De Tabasco, 1517-1525". *EDĀHI Boletín Científico De Ciencias Sociales Y Humanidades Del Icshu*, no. 10 (2022).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Vásquez Dávila, M.A., and H. Hernández. "La Cosmovisión De Los Chontales De Tabasco: Notas Preliminares". *América Indígena* 54, no. (1-2) (1994).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Fergus, R., and K. Hull. "Ethno-ornithological Research Among the Chontal Maya of Tabasco, Mexico", 2013.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Lorente Fernández, D.. *Mythology and Multifunctionality of Thunder God Among the Chontal of Tabasco*. México: Dirección de Etnología y Antropología Social, Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia, Ciudad de México, 2016.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Hernández Granada, A.. *Los Chontales Prehispánicos De Tabasco-campeche : En Busca De Su Identidad Étnica*. Tesis de Maestría en Estudios Mesoamericanos. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México , 2018.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), González Torres, Y.. *Diccionario De Mitología Y Religión De Mesoamérica*. México: Ediciones Larousse, 1991.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Campos, J.. *Bajo El Signo De Ix Bolon*. México: Fondo de Cultura Económica-Instituto de Cultura de Tabasco, 1988.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Mejía Perez Campos, E.. "Comalcalco". *Arqueología*. Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia - INAH, 1992.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Fita, D., E. Naranjo, E. Estrada-Lugo, R. Mariaca, and E. Bello. "Symbolism and Ritual Practices Related to Hunting in Maya Communities from Central Quintana Roo, Mexico.". *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*. 11 (2015).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Van Broekhoven, L.. *La Tradición Oral De Los Yokoyinik 'ob De Tamulté. Costumbres, Creencias, Cuentos Y Continuidad*. Netherlands: Tesis de Maestría, Universidad de Leiden., 1995.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Sigal, P.. *From Moon Goddesses to Virgins. The Colonization of Yucatecan Maya Sexual Desire*. Texas: University of Texas Press , 2000.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Gonlin, N., and J.C. Lohse. *Commoner Ritual and Ideology in Ancient Mesoamerica*. Colorado: University Press of Colorado, 2007.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Sharer, R.J., and L.P. Traxler. *The Ancient Maya*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2005.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Tozzer, A.M.. *Landa's Relación De Los Cosas De Yucatán*. Cambridge: Harvard University, 1941.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), López, A.. "Los Ritos. Un Juego De Definiciones". *Arqueología Mexicana*, no. 34 (1988): 4-17.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Nájera, M.I.. *El Don De La Sangre En El Equilibrio Cósmico*. Mexico City: Centro de Estudios Mayas, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, 1987.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Landa, Fray D.. *Relación De Las Cosas De Yucatán, [sixteenth Century]*. Mexico City: Porrúa, 1982.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Joralemon, D.. "Ritual Blood-sacrifice Among the Ancient Maya, Part I". *Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society* 118, no. 2 (1974): 59-106.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Scott, A.M., and J.E. Brady. "Human Remains in Lowland Maya Caves: Problems of Interpretation". In *Stone Houses and Earth Lords: Maya Religion in the Cave Context*. Boulder: University Press of Colorado, 2005.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Munson, J., V. Amati, M. Collard, and M.J. Macri. "Classic Maya Bloodletting and the Cultural Evolution of Religious Rituals: Quantifying Patterns of Variation in Hieroglyphic Texts". *Plos One* 9, no. 9 (2014).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), McLeod, A.. "Sacrifice: A Maya Conception of a Misunderstood and Underappreciated Component of Well-being". *Science, Religion and Culture* 6, no. 1 (2019): 34-41.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Stuart, D.. "Royal Auto-sacrifice Among the Maya: A Study of Image and Meaning". *RES: Anthropology and Aesthetics*, 1984, 6-20.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Šprajc, I., T. Inomata, and A.F. Aveni. "Origins of Mesoamerican

Astronomy and Calendar: Evidence from the Olmec and Maya Regions". *Science Advances* 9, no. 1 (2023).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Lucero, L.J.. "The Politics of Ritual. The Emergence of Classic Maya Rulers". *Current Anthropology* 44, no. 4 (2003): 523-58.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Inomata, T.. "Plazas, Performers, and Spectators: Political Theaters of the Classic Maya". *Current Anthropology* 47, no. 5 (2006): 805-42.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Lentz, D.L., T.L. Hamilton, S.A. Meyers, N.P. Dunning, K. Reese-Taylor, A.A. Hernández, D.S. Walker, E.J. Tepe, A.F. Esquivel, and A.A. Weiss. "Psychoactive and Other Ceremonial Plants from a 2,000-year-old Maya Ritual Deposit at Yaxnohcah, Mexico". *Plos One* 19, no. 4 (2024).

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Blainey, M.G.. "Techniques of Luminosity: Iron-ore Mirrors and Entheogenic Shamanism Among the Ancient Maya". In *Manufactured Light: Mirrors in the Mesoamerican Realm*. Canada: Trent University, 2016.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Lucero, L.J.. "The Collapse of the Classic Maya: A Case for the Role of Water Control". *American Anthropologist* 104, no. 3 (2002): 814-26.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Roys, R.L.. *The Political Geography of the Yucatan Maya*. Washington: Carnegie Institution of Washington, 1957.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Houston, S., J. Robertson, and D. Stuart. "The Language of Classic Maya Inscriptions". *Current Anthropology* 41, no. 3 (2000): 321-56.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Kettunen, h., and C. Helmke. *Introduction to Maya Hieroglyphs: 10th European Maya Workshop Handbook*. Leiden: Wayeb and Leiden University, 2010.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espíritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Flores López, J.M.. *Chontales De Tabasco*. Mexico: Comisión Nacional para el Desarrollo de los Pueblos Indígenas, 2006.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Silva de la Mora, F.C.. "The Cultural Landscapes of Maya Roads: The Material Evidence and a GIS Study from the Maya Lowlands of Chiapas and Tabasco, Mexico". *Latin American Antiquity* 34, no. 4 (2023): 804-20.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Joyce, M.. "Ancient Maya Political Organization". In *Lowland Maya Civilizations in the Eighth Century A.D.*. Washington: Dumbarton Oaks, 1993.

Reference: The Chontal Maya (Yoko t'anob), Incháustegui, C.. *Las Márgenes Del Tabasco Chontal*. Mexico: Gobierno del Estado de Tabasco, 1987.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Sí, Scholes, F., and R. Roys. *The Maya Chontal Indians of Acalan-tixchel; a Contribution to the History and Ethnography of the Yucatan Peninsula*. Oklahoma Press, 1968.

Reference: En el hogar, Únicamente en espacios religiosos públicos, En algunos espacios públicos, Gallegos Gómora, M.J., and R. Armijo Torres. "Las Figurillas Mayas De Tabasco, México: Contextos Y Narraciones Del Clásico Tardío". *Figurines*, no. 6 (2021).

Reference: Sí, Muñoz-Salinas, E., D. Cook, M. Castillo, T. Beach, and S. Luzzadder-Beach. "Four Millennia of Geomorphic Change and Human Settlement in the Lower Usumacinta-grijalva River Basin, Mexico.". *Progress in Physical Geography: Earth and Environment* 47, no. 2 (2023).

Reference: El campo lo desconoce, Geller, P., K. Reese-Taylor, and M. Zender. *Fit to Be Tied: Funerary Practices Among the Prehispanic Maya*, 2006. .

Reference: Estimated population, numeric: 4500, Ciudad Ruiz, A., and A. Lacadena García-Gallo. "Tamactún-acalán: Interpretación De Una Hegemonía Política Maya De Los Siglos XIV-XVI", no. 87 (2001).

Reference: Sí, Ringle, W. M., and G.E. Stuart. *Of Mice and Monkeys: The Value and Meaning of Π016, the God C Hieroglyph*. United States of America: Center for Maya Research, 1988.

Reference: Sí, Lacadena, A., and A. Ciudad Ruiz. "Reflexiones Sobre Estructura Política Maya Clásica". In *Anatomía De Una Civilización. Aproximaciones Interdisciplinarias a La Cultura Maya*. España: Sociedad Española de Estudios Mayas, 1998.

year-old Maya Ritual Deposit at Yaxnohcah, Mexico". Plos One 19, no. 4 (2024).

Reference: Sí, Blainey, M.G.. "Techniques of Luminosity: Iron-ore Mirrors and Entheogenic Shamanism Among the Ancient Maya". In *Manufactured Light: Mirrors in the Mesoamerican Realm*. Canada: Trent University, 2016.

Reference: Sí, Lucero, L.J.. "The Collapse of the Classic Maya: A Case for the Role of Water Control". *American Anthropologist* 104, no. 3 (2002): 814-26. ,

Reference: No, Roys, R.L.. *The Political Geography of the Yucatan Maya*. Washington: Carnegie Institution of Washington, 1957. ,

Reference: El campo lo desconoce, Tiesler, V., and A. Cucina, eds.. *New Perspectives on Human Sacrifice and Ritual Body Treatments in Ancient Maya Society*. Edited by V. Tiesler and A. Cucina. New York: Springer, 2006. , , , , , , , ,

Reference: Sí, Kettunen, h., and C. Helmke. *Introduction to Maya Hieroglyphs: 10th European Maya Workshop Handbook*. Leiden: Wayeb and Leiden University, 2010.

Reference: Sí, Rubio, M.Á., and M.Y. Martínez. *De Sombras, Sapos Y Espíritus. Relatos Sobre Los Días De Muertos Entre Los Chontales De Tabasco Y Los Pames De Querétaro*. Mexico: UNAM-Conaculta, 2006. , , , , ,

Reference: Sí, Incháustegui, C.. *Las Márgenes Del Tabasco Chontal*. Mexico: Gobierno del Estado de Tabasco, 1987.